

Delineating urban areas through satellite-derived building footprints

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February 27, 2022

Summary

Delineating the spatial extent of urban phenomena at different scales is one of the core challenges researchers, planners and policy makers are faced with. This paper proposes to use satellite-derived building footprints and a clustering approach to create a hierarchy of parcels of urban land in the contiguous United states. This hierarchy is used to analyse three urban phenomena - urban form, urban spatial extent and megaregional integration. The most stable parcels from the hierarchy capture 79% of the US population and are similar to census defined urban centres. Furthermore, the hierarchy is used to show the decentralised urban form of these parcels. Lastly, the hierarchy is used to measure the morphological integration of the parcels into large scale urban phenomena - megaregions.

KEYWORDS: new forms of data, urban analytics, urban form, megaregions, city size.

1 Introduction

Delineating the spatial extent of urban phenomena is one of the core challenges researchers, planners and policy makers are faced with. Defining the base spatial units of analysis, is the first step in analysing urbanisation, employment decentralisation or megaregional integration. Sub-optimal definitions do not represent functional reality appropriately and may, at worst, compromise the effectiveness of research and policy implementation and evaluation. This can happen at different scales. Poor city delineations misrepresent the degree of urbanization and can lead to scepticism towards the benefits of it (Roberts et al., 2017). Analysis into employment decentralisation at the intra-metropolitan scale is affected by the delineation of both of the area under study and the number and boundaries of urban centres within it (Möck and Küpper, 2020). At an even larger scale, research into the potential number and boundaries of "megaregions" - the integration of cities and metropolitan areas into clusters - is also affected by delineation choices (Wheeler, 2015).

There are numerous ways in which researchers have attempted to quantitatively define urban boundaries at different scales. These methods rely on combining fundamental units, based on similarity of

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attributes or functional relationships. Popular choices of units are small scale administrative areas - census tracts, counties Nelson (2020) - or cells and hexagons derived from gridding the territory under analysis (Florczyk et al., 2019). These can be grouped together to form urban areas in three ways: first, based on functional relationships such as commuter flows; second, on spatial contiguity and characteristics of the units - population density or night lights; or third, on combinations of the previous two approaches. With the rising availability of new forms of data (Arribas-Bel and Sanz-Gracia, 2014), researchers are able to look at other units and interactions - tweets, mobile phone data , location-based social networks.

The contributions of the paper to the literature are two. First, this paper takes advantage of new forms of data and delineates urban boundaries in the contiguous United States, based on only on the footprints of individual buildings and a machine learning approach. For this purpose it uses 129 591 852 building footprints, generated by applying computer vision algorithms on satellite imagery (Heris et al., 2020).

Second, this paper modifies a clustering algorithm - HDSCAN (Campello et al., 2015) - to account for the large size of the dataset and to particular issues related to footprint extraction from satellite images. This results in a nested hierarchy of parcels of land, delineated based on the the location of individual buildings and their local built environment density. The hierarchy is used in three ways: first to define urban boundaries, second to describe their morphological form and third to analyse the requirements for the integration of the delineated areas at a megaregional scale.

The main advantage of this paper’s approach is its flexibility. Urban areas are delineated using relative values of ‘high’ and ‘low’ which vary locally as inferred from the surrounding building footprints at a particular place. There is no single density, radius or model requirements imposed on the identified boundaries.

Other advantages come from the use of buildings as the fundamental unit in the construction of urban areas. There is no need to aggregate administrative units or grid cells or reliance on any population data. Furthermore, the method can be applied globally and has the potential to track temporal changes in real-time.

2 Data

The data used in this paper comes from the Microsoft Cognitive Toolkit (CNTK). It consists of 129 591 852 computer vision generated building footprints extracted from Bing imagery, covering all 50 US states. Figure 1 shows the available data for Washington D.C.

Figure 1: Building footprints data for D.C.

We use six additional datasets as to carry out a series of comparisons, aimed at better understanding our results - GHSL population grid (Florczyk et al., 2019), GHSL Urban Centre boundaries, Tiger Line Census Urban Centres (CUC) boundaries, the megaregion delineations from the America 2050 project (Hagler, 2009), the official local incorporated place boundaries in the United States (towns and cities) and finally the census metropolitan area delineations.

resulting areas ranges from large clusters of cities - i.e. one area covers both Washington D.C. and Baltimore- to small towns with populations of five thousand. The number of buildings footprints in each cluster is highly correlated with the actual census population with statistically significant results - spearman .95 and pearson .95. In general the delineated areas are much larger than the official boundaries similarly to the results of other population based delineation approaches - e.g. GHS settlement layer Florczyk et al. (2019).

Figure 3: Building footprints data for D.C.

Sample comparisons of the fifteen largest cities and rand index comparisons using the whole data show that the delineated areas are more similar to the census defined urban Cent than to GHS urban centre delineations. Figure 3 shows a comparison of the areas in the northeast of the US. The final results incorporate more diverse urban forms and are more similar to the larger census defined urban areas. Further random index and spatial polygon comparisons show that the resulting parcels of land can be directly used as urban delineations for areas over 25k, while they need additional work for other sparser populated areas.

The results further suggests that the majority of metropolitan areas in the contiguous US contain

one dominant delineated area, however many of these areas cross the census defined metropolitan boundaries. When the hierarchy is used to analyse the form of each of the delineated areas it is found the majority of them have of multiple dense cores in a complex relationship to each other.

Table 1: Megaregional morphological integration

Megaregion	Radius in metres
Northeastern Megalopolis	3914.602623
Atlantic Piedmont	5156.625124
Cascadia	6563.781295
Midwest	6700.217923
Florida	7383.171417
Texas Triangle	8865.429789
Arizona Sun Corridor	14399.868959
North California	16849.370273
Frontrange	19274.251142
South California	22335.506380
Gulf Coast	24368.532630

Another interesting insight from Figure 2 is the non-existence of delineated areas at the megaregional scale. Nevertheless, the hierarchy can also be used to see how close to being morphologically integrated the proposed America 2050 megaregions are at this time. This is shown in Table 1. The most integrated megaregions based on our approach and data, in order of relative morphological integration, are: Northeastern metropolis, Atlantic Piedmont, Cascadia, Florida, Texas Triangle and Arizona Sun Corridor. Interestingly, our results also suggest that the Midwest, South California, Front range and Gulf Coast America2050 megaregions cannot be delineated at all. This is due to the large differences in the densities and numbers of buildings in the proposed megaregional boundaries. In order for these differences to be incorporated in a single a parcel in the hierarchy, the parcel must span a large portion of the entire US land mass and also include multiple other megaregions.

5 Biography

Daniel Arribas-Bel is a Senior Lecturer in Geographic Data Science at the Department of Geography and Planning , member of the Geographic Data Science Lab, at the University of Liverpool (UK).

Alex Singleton is a Professor of Geographic Information Science at the University of Liverpool, where he was appointed as a Lecturer in 2010. Previously he held research positions at University College London, where he was also awarded a PhD in 2007. He completed a BSc in Geography at the University of Manchester, graduating with a First-class honours degree in 2003.

Krasen Samardzhiev is a final year PhD student at the Geographic Data Science Lab, at the University of Liverpool (UK).

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